

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF HIGH ORDER THINKING SKILLS IN THEMATIC INTEGRATED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

One of the objectives of curriculum change is to increase students' readiness in thinking at the level. In the implementation of the 2013 curriculum, especially in thematic learning, this was new in elementary schools. For this reason, this study is intended to reveal teachers' perceptions of the skills of high-level thinkers in primary schools. Based on the purpose of the research, the research design chosen was survey research. With a cross-sectional survey design. Teacher perceptions can be obtained through indicators, understanding, and implementation and teacher evaluation of the application of High Order Thinking skills.

Keywords: creative thinking, critical thinking reasoning, thematic integrated, high order thinking skills

1. Introduction

For some teachers, understand that learning cannot be separated from reasoning. In Students in primary schools and even early children can use their reasoning in daily life. Like trying to play together using blocks to form a building. Elementary school students have also been able to make their choices when shopping at the school canteen. Food or objects that can be purchased according to the amount of money they have. These concepts should be applicable in the learning process of students.

Some teachers, understand that learning cannot be separated from reasoning. In learning, students are often asked to remember, memorize, repeat a material, numbers, quantities, and procedures. If so students will certainly have difficulty in solving problems that require higher-order thinking skills.

Matthews & Jo Lally (2010) cite a number of opinions about thinking skills with a fairly simple but clear definition. According to Valerie Wilson, thinking is interpreted as "the process of cognition,

knowing, remembering, perceiving and attending", while skills are "the acts of collecting and sorting information; analysis, drawing conclusions, brainstorming, problem solving, evaluating options, planning, monitoring, decision making and reflecting ". Furthermore, thinking skills are interpreted as a simple way of looking at problems. The UK Department for Education and Skills explained that thinking skills consist of information processing, reasoning, discovery, creative thinking and evaluation, so that they can be categorized as critical thinking, creative thinking, problem solving and decision making. By considering all of these explanations, thinking skills can be expressed as a structured cognitive process that helps in making, understanding, and solving problems and issues to reach a decision.

Reasoning Ability

Reasoning is a thought process that seeks to link known facts or evidence to a conclusion, keraf (1982). Not much different from reasoning according to

Suriasumantri (1999) is a thought process in drawing a conclusion in the form of knowledge and has certain characteristics in finding the truth. So that the knowledge produced by reasoning has a basis of truth, the thought process must be done in a certain way so that the drawing of new conclusions is considered valid (valid), thus the ability of reasoning is the ability of students to think logically according to a certain frame of mind. The process of thinking logically in dealing with problems by following existing provisions and ending with conclusions.

"Reasoning is a special kind of thinking in which inference takes place, in which conclusions are drawn from premises" Copi (in Sadiq, 2007: 3), the sentence explains that reasoning as an activity, process or activity of thinking to draw a conclusion or make a new statement based on several statements that are known to be true or that are assumed to be true or that which are assumed to be true are called premises

Reasoning is an important aspect that must be developed in mathematics learning is no exception in elementary schools. This is in accordance with the opinion of Wahyudin (2008) that reasoning and proof must be an important part in the experience of mathematical students from kindergarten to 12th grade, in this case elementary schools are also included in the category.

Creative Thinking Skills

Mathematical creative thinking is original and reflective thinking and produces a complex product in mathematical problems. Thinking involves the synthesis of ideas, building new ideas and determining their effectiveness. In useful with the desired command, the indicators of eligibility, usefulness or value of creative thinking have been met. While authenticity can be demonstrated or is part of the novelty. So indicators or components of thinking can include fluency, flexibility and novelty.

addition, creative thinking is also related to the ability to make decisions and produce new products. This is in accordance with the opinion of Krulik (1999: 139) who defines creative thinking as original thinking and produces a complex result, which includes formulating ideas, generating new ideas, and determining their effectiveness. This understanding shows that creative thinking is a process that is used to bring or bring up a new idea that is useful that these ideas had never before existed.

Meanwhile, Munandar (in Huda, 2011) explained that the understanding of creative thinking is the ability to find many possible answers to a problem, where the emphasis is on the quantity, accuracy, and diversity of answers. This understanding shows that one's ability to think creatively higher, if the person is able to show many possible answers to a problem. But all the answers must be in accordance with the problem and right. Thus creative thinking can be interpreted as the ability to bring up new ideas that are useful for solving a problem whose emphasis is on the quality, accuracy, and diversity of these ideas.

To assess the creative thinking of children and adults often used "The Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking (TTCT)". Three key components assessed in creativity using TTCT are fluency, flexibility and novelty. Fluency refers to the number of ideas created in response to an order. Flexibility is seen in approach changes when responding to commands. Novelty is the authenticity of ideas created in response to commands. In each component, if the command response is required to be appropriate, appropriate or

Communication Skills

Communication in general can be interpreted as a way to convey a message from the messenger to the recipient of the message to notify, opinion, or behavior both verbally, or in writing. In communicating these things that must be considered is how to make a message conveyed by someone can be understood

by others because of the achievement of good communication, if the sender and recipient of the message can receive and understand messages clearly and accurately.

The parties involved in the communication event in the classroom are the teacher and students. In the process of learning mathematics in class, communication of mathematical ideas can take place between teacher and student, between material and students, and between students and students. Every time we communicate an idea, the idea must be adapted to the ability of people invited to communicate. Without it, communication will only take place from one direction and not reach the target. This is a very important thing, because if not, the communication will not be effective.

Communication skills are important when discussions between students take place, where students are expected to be able to state, explain, describe, hear, ask and work together so that they can bring students to a deep understanding of mathematics. Students are given the opportunity to work collecting, confirming, and presenting data. They listen to ideas from one another, discuss them together then draw conclusions that become opinions between themselves and / or the group. Thus, they learn to show good progress on their mathematical communication skills because they have done most of the communication and construct their own knowledge.

can **not be said to be** a problem. When students find a problem, there has been a difference in balance (disequilibrium) with the initial state (equilibrium) before.

The ability to think at a higher level is an ability to think that not only requires the ability to remember, but also requires other higher abilities, such as the ability to think creatively and critically. The next problem is how to teach explicit thinking skills and integrate them with

Problem Solving Capability

Problem solving requires knowledge and experience skills to be able to obtain new things, face and overcome obstacles, to achieve goals and valid solutions to problems.

Skills and knowledge in problem solving can be passed through the following stages: expressing methods and solutions, focusing on problems, making careful observations, making connections, identifying, exploring patterns, and asking or making questions of problems and understanding of problems to be solved. Understanding of the problems that must be done before seeking a solution or problem solving is to make plans, implement plans that have been made and look back on what should be done after completion.

Problem solving is considered a standard of ability that must be possessed by students after attending mathematics learning. Mathematical problem-solving ability is an action to solve a problem or process that uses skills and knowledge in solving mathematical problems. Problem solving skills are very useful for students in mathematics itself, the relevance of mathematics to other subjects and in real world life. A problem usually contains situations that encourage students to complete, will but do not know firsthand what should be done to solve them. If a **problem is** given to a student and the student immediately knows how to solve it correctly, then the problem

learning material that can help students develop their thinking ability.

The effort made by the government is by changing the curriculum so that it contains high-level thinking skills. These changes were welcomed by various teachers. There are various responses related to the application of higher order thinking skills in elementary schools. There are teachers who welcome the application of higher level thinking skills,

There are those who think that high level thinking skills are complicated and difficult to apply, and some even do not understand how to apply of high orde thinking skills in learning.

2. METHOD

This study aims to describe teachers' perceptions of higher-level thinking skills in elementary school. Based on these objectives the research design chosen was a survey. The survey design chosen was a *cross-sectional survey design*, i.e. the data was collected at a certain time and did not measure changes that occurred in the individuals sampled (Wiersma and Jurs, 2009: 196). The *cross-sectional* survey design was chosen for the following reasons (Cohen et al, 2000: 179) . This study was single, namely primary school teachers' perceptions of higher -

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study began by designing a data collection instrument about teacher perceptions. For this reason, a questionnaire was designed to be further validated by experts. The questionnaire

order thinking skills. The population of this study were all elementary school teachers in north teak city . Whereas the target population in this study only taken on teachers who teach in grades IV, V and VI elementary school. The sample in this study is all individuals in the target population that have been selected, also known as *census studies* (Creswell, 2008: 394; Wiersma and Ju rs, 2009 : 194), which is a number of 48 teachers. *Census Census study* was conducted because the population is small and makes it possible to take the data one by one. In addition, *census study* also allows the conclusion that represents the entire population. All of the samples again fill out a questionnaire about the perception of teachers' skills think high level in elementary school.

contained questions about the understanding, implementation and assessment of teachers on the application of higher-order thinking skills at primary school. From data collection in the field using a questionnaire, the following data were obtained.

Indicator	Category		
	High	is on	Low
Perception	40 %	45%	15%
Understanding	60%	35%	5%
Implementation	30%	45%	25%
Assessment	25%	65%	20%

From the table above, it can be seen that the level of understanding, implementation, and assessment are at different percentage levels. The teacher has a good understanding of the application of higher order thinking skills, even though the implementation and assessment have an understanding in the medium and low categories. After an analysis of good understanding is obtained from schools that have first implemented the 2013 curriculum. Furthermore, item analysis of the statements given results

shows that (1) teachers who have high qualifications have a high perception of the application of higher-order thinking skills, (2) teachers are constrained in designing problems that can facilitate students' high-level thinking (3) teachers have difficulty motivating students to be able to communicate ideas in the learning process, (4) teachers have a fairly good understanding of the form of assessment used. (5) The results of the assessment of higher-order thinking skills cannot yet be used as a follow-up material in developing

student understanding. (6) The teacher measures students' high-level thinking skills using tests. This shows that the teacher has

The procedure of implementation and evaluation. For this reason, it is necessary to design a guide to the implementation of the learning process and authentic assessment as a guide for the teacher in carrying out high-level thinking learning.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Uni's findings reveal that (1) elementary school teachers have a good understanding of high level thinking skills (2) teachers' perceptions of the implementation and assessment of high level thinking skills in primary schools need to be improved again.

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